

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract.

This article deals with the cross analysis of economic terms in English and Uzbek languages. Nowadays, economics is becoming one of the major fields in the development of country. Moreover, English has already taken the first place in the line of world languages, respectively. Economic terms and their use in both languages will be analyzed with examples in this work.

Keywords: arbitration, protectorate, ticker, exchange, customs union, state budget, a closed monopoly, timely salary, payment transaction.

For the last few decades, the number of people who are attracted by the chance of working on economical terms has been increasing at an alarming speed. The most well-known professors of our country have added their considerable portion to the development of this field. For example, the first DCs of economics of our region X. Rakhmankulov wrote over 15 books about this field. Especially, "Biznes va Tadbirkorlik sirlari" is devoted to economical terms, their definitions and etymology. Another prominent books "Iqtisodiyotga oid matnlar tarjimasining o'ziga xosligi" by Salimova N. and "Iqtisodiyotga oid atamalar va tushunchalar izohli lug'ati" by Zoyirov Z. play an important role for learners of economics.

Words related to economics are divided into two types:

1. Common economic words – which are used by any people in everyday life. For example: market, money, fortune, sale, tax, debt and other common words that are understandable for everyone.
2. Economic terms – which are used in the sphere of the people deal with economics. The difference between economic terms and common economic words is economic terms possess only one meaning and we can not use them with other aims.

Economic terms are considered as a very wide field and consist of three main subfields:

1. Terms related to Bank: currency, sum, price, coupon, cheque, credit, lease contract, interest rate, credit risk, active, passive, problem loan, interest margin, export credit.
2. Terms related to Tax: tax object, tax subject, tax sources, tax norm, tax unit, tax rate, tax declaration, tax policy, value added tax, excise tax, income tax, profit, land tax, property tax.
3. Terms related to Finance: financial policy, financial control, finance function, financial theory, financial resource, financial relationship, proprietary relationship, state budget, depreciation fund, depreciation allowances.

As it comes to the cross analysis of economic terms, they are translated in two ways. Some terms are translated from Uzbek into English without change in terms of meaning and form. For instance:

Agent (agent) - A fiduciary acting in trade and other fields within the scope of the mandate and for the benefit of other persons.

Arbitration (arbitraj) - State organization for resolving property disputes between state enterprises, organizations and institutions.

Audit (audit) - In order to determine its reliability and compliance with the laws of finance and economic operations and other regulatory acts, as well as with the requirements of accounting or other financial reporting, independent examination by authorized auditors and economic entities financial statement analysis.

Limit (limit) – credit limit in amounts.

Protectorate (protektorat) - It is a form of economic and political dependence, in which the country is subordinate to the most powerful state, while maintaining its state structure formally.

Renting (renting) - Short-term rental of machines and equipment, usually up to six months, without the right of further ownership by the lessee.

Sif (sif) - One of the terms of delivery of goods in international trade.

String (string) - A unit of auction sales representing a grouping of lots of similar quality.

Trend (trend) – a direction indicating a change in grades.

Ticker (tiker) - A telegraphic communication system that continuously provides the last price of the sale of securities on the stock exchange and the volume of transactions with securities.

Other terms own some changes in terms of forms while translating from English into Uzbek:

Exchange (ayirboshlash) - Interactivity between people in the economy, manifested directly or in the form of exchange of labor products.

Stock market panic (birja vahimasi) - The most acute period of a stock market crisis, characterized by a sudden and catastrophic fall in the price of stocks, primarily stocks.

Customs union (bojxona ittifoqi) - An agreement between two or more countries on the abolition of customs duties.

Timely salary (vaqtbay ish haqi) - It is a form of payment for labor, in which the salary paid to the worker depends on the amount of time worked, qualification and quality of work.

State budget (davlat budjeti) - A comprehensive estimate of government revenue and expenditure by sources of revenue and major channels of expenditure.

A closed monopoly (yopiq monopoliya) - A monopoly protected by legal prohibitions on competition.

International means of payment (xalqaro to'lov vositalari) - Means of covering international credit obligations, previously - gold, now - convertible currencies, international units of account.

Payment transaction (to'lov oboroti) - A part of monetary circulation, in which money acts as a means of payment and is used to cover obligations.

General equivalent (umumiy ekvivalent) - A single commodity that represents the value of other commodities and serves for the mutual exchange of goods.

Import agreement (import bitimi) - Purchases of goods or services that reduce the amount of foreign currency held by certain individuals, firms, and governments of that country.

In conclusion, while dealing with this article I have been aware of how rich economic terms in Uzbek and English languages are. In the translation of each economic term, its composition and its elements, the style of the text also play an important role. Although some terms do not demand change in translation, other parts require special use of cross analysis.

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